

Supplementary Data

Vetiver-Based Nature-Based Solutions for Sustainable Landslide Mitigation: Hydromechanical Slope Response under Groundwater and Multi-Hazard Conditions

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This Supplementary Data document provides the complementary methodological, graphical, photographic, and numerical information supporting the results presented in the main manuscript. The contents are organized to follow the overall structure of the study and include: (S1) additional information on the numerical implementation, model configuration, and complementary PLAXIS 2D graphical outputs; (S2) a schematic representation of the adopted groundwater configuration; (S3) photographic documentation of bare-soil sampling and initial sample handling; (S4) photographic documentation of laboratory procedures and Atterberg limits determination; and (S5–S10) the complete numerical datasets obtained from PLAXIS 2D simulations for the representative soil types MH, CH, and ML, considering different slope geometries, groundwater conditions, external loading, and combined seismic scenarios.

The numerical tables include both natural and Vetiver-reinforced cases, allowing direct comparison of the vegetation effect on factor of safety and total displacement. Together, these supplementary materials enhance the transparency, reproducibility, and interpretability of the methodological approach and numerical results discussed in the main manuscript.

All simulations incorporate a steady-state groundwater table located between 70% and 80% of the slope height, allowing for a realistic representation of hydro-mechanical behavior. The datasets include both natural soil conditions and Vetiver-reinforced scenarios, enabling direct comparison of vegetation effects on slope stability and deformation.

S1. Additional Information on the Numerical Implementation, Model Configuration, and Complementary Graphical Outputs

This section provides supplementary information on the numerical implementation adopted in this study, including the model configuration and complementary graphical outputs obtained from PLAXIS 2D simulations. The objective of this supplementary material is to enhance the transparency and reproducibility of the numerical approach by documenting the geometric setup, domain definition, and representation of vegetation-induced reinforcement used in the slope stability analyses. The figures presented herein serve as visual support to the methodology described in the main manuscript and complement the quantitative results reported in Section 3.

The numerical analyses were performed using PLAXIS 2D under plane strain conditions, considering representative slope geometries, appropriate boundary conditions, and soil domains consistent with the geotechnical properties defined in the experimental program. A superficial reinforced zone was incorporated along the slope face to simulate the mechanical contribution of vegetation, following the conceptual framework adopted in the main study. The graphical outputs included in Figures S1–S9 illustrate the configuration of the numerical models for different soil types (MH, CH, and ML) and geometric scenarios, providing a visual reference of the modelling assumptions and facilitating the interpretation and replication of the numerical simulations.

Figure S1.1. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for MH soil under configuration 0.5

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ for MH soil under a 0.5H:1V slope configuration. The results correspond to a displacement magnitude on the order of 10^{-3} , with a maximum value of approximately 0.07 mm.

Figure S1.2. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for MH soil under configuration 1.0

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ for MH soil with a 1H:1V slope geometry. The actual displacement level is on the order of 10^{-3} , with a maximum total displacement of approximately 0.12 mm.

Figure S1.3. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for MH soil under configuration 1.75

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ obtained for MH soil with a 1.75H:1V slope geometry. Although the output is labeled in meters, the effective displacement magnitude is on the order of 10^{-3} , resulting in a maximum total displacement of approximately 0.61 mm

Figure S1.4. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for CH soil under configuration 0.5

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ for CH soil under a 0.5H:1V slope configuration. The contour plot is displayed in meters, but the actual displacement level is on the order of 10^{-3} , with a maximum value of approximately 0.19 mm.

Figure S1.5. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for CH soil under configuration 1.0

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ for CH soil with a 1H:1V slope geometry. The results are shown in meters in the software output, but the effective displacement magnitude is on the order of 10^{-3} , giving a maximum total displacement of approximately 0.56 mm.

Figure S1.6. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for CH soil under configuration 1.75

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ obtained from the PLAXIS 2D analysis for CH soil under a 1.75H:1V slope configuration. Although the plot is displayed in meters, the reported values correspond to a scaled range on the order of 10^{-3} ; therefore, the maximum total displacement is approximately 2.95 mm.

Figure S1.7. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for ML soil under configuration 0.5

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ for ML soil with a 1.75H:1V slope geometry. The displacement field corresponds to a scaled range on the order of 10^{-3} , giving a maximum total displacement of approximately 0.32 mm.

Figure S1.8. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for ML soil under configuration 1.0

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ for ML soil with a 1H:1V slope geometry. Despite being displayed in meters, the output indicates a small deformation level, with a maximum total displacement of approximately 3.25 mm.

Figure S1.9. Numerical configuration of the vegetated slope model for ML soil under configuration 1.75

Note: Total displacement magnitude $|u|$ for ML soil under a 0.5H:1V slope configuration. The maximum total displacement is approximately 8.81 mm.

S2. Schematic representation of the adopted groundwater configuration

This supplementary figure provides a schematic representation of the groundwater configuration adopted in the study. The selected configuration is based on the typical slope morphology identified in the investigated area and on the observed groundwater conditions, which indicate the presence of permeable subsurface materials and a groundwater level fluctuating within the upper portion of the slope profile.

Figure S2. Groundwater table position within the representative slope configuration

The subsurface was characterized as predominantly permeable, and the adopted groundwater level was defined based on field observations indicating fluctuations within approximately 70–80% of the slope height under historically high groundwater conditions.

S3. Photographic Documentation of Bare-Soil Sampling and Initial Sample Handling

This section provides complementary photographic documentation of the bare-soil sampling procedure and the initial handling of the collected specimens prior to laboratory testing. The images are included to support the reproducibility of the experimental methodology and to document the procedures adopted to preserve the in situ condition of the material as much as possible during extraction, transport, and storage. Bare-soil sampling was carried out at a depth of 1.7 m to avoid the influence of organic matter and to ensure that the geomechanical characterization represented the soil condition prior to root reinforcement by the studied vegetation.

Figure S3.1. Bare-soil sampling at a depth of 1.7 m

Note: This figure shows the field sampling procedure for the bare soils, conducted at a depth of 1.7 m. This depth was selected to avoid the presence of organic matter and to ensure that the analysed material represented the pre-reinforcement geomechanical condition of the soil, prior to the influence of plant roots

Figure S3.2. Storage of soil samples prior to laboratory testing

Note: This figure illustrates the storage procedure adopted for the collected soil samples before laboratory testing. The undisturbed specimens were sealed in hermetic plastic bags to preserve their natural moisture condition as much as possible during transport. The transfer time from the sampling site to the laboratory was approximately 1 h. Moisture-content determination started 3 h after sampling, whereas the remaining laboratory tests were conducted 24 h after extraction.

S4. Photographic Documentation of Laboratory Procedures and Atterberg Limits Determination

This section provides complementary photographic documentation of the laboratory procedures applied during the geotechnical characterization program, with particular emphasis on the determination of the Atterberg limits. These images are included to support the reproducibility of the experimental methodology and to visually document the stages followed in the laboratory for evaluating the consistency-related index properties of the studied soils.

The Atterberg limits test has long been recognized as a fundamental procedure for describing the mechanical behavior of fine-grained soils as a function of water content. In the present study, the liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index were determined to characterize the consistency and plasticity response of the tested materials. The test procedure was conducted in accordance with the applicable standard indicated in the main manuscript, and its main stages are illustrated in the supplementary figures included in this section.

S4. Laboratory procedure for the determination of Atterberg Limits

Note: This figure presents the laboratory procedure followed for the determination of the Atterberg limits, including the preparation and handling stages required to obtain the liquid limit and plastic limit of the studied soils.

S5. Baseline FS results with groundwater

Table S5. Factor of Safety (FS) under baseline conditions with groundwater (Plaxis 2D)

Slope (H:V)	MH	CH	ML	MH (Vetiver)	CH (Vetiver)	ML (Vetiver)
0.5:1	1.474	1.898	1.102	1.434	1.788	1.104
1:01	1.788	2.16	1.468	1.8	2.166	1.501
1.75:1	2.132	2.454	1.837	2.118	2.451	1.84

Note: All simulations incorporate a groundwater table located between 70–80% of the slope height. The results indicate that vegetation provides moderate improvements in FS, particularly in ML soils, where reinforcement prevents the system from approaching critical instability thresholds.

S6. Displacement under baseline conditions with groundwater

This section reports the total displacement results obtained from finite element simulations under baseline conditions, considering groundwater influence and vegetation reinforcement.

Table S6. Total displacement under baseline conditions with groundwater (mm)

Slope (H:V)	MH	CH	ML	MH (Vetiver)	CH (Vetiver)	ML (Vetiver)
0.5:1	99.11	47.68	14.72	71.92	185	8.805
1:01	112.4	360.8	129.9	124.7	561.1	13.28
1.75:1	1341	3454	1427	610.2	2951	316.4

Note: Displacements are expressed in millimeters (mm). Results show that Vetiver significantly reduces deformation in ML soils, while higher variability in CH soils reflects sensitivity to pore pressure and slope geometry under saturated conditions.

S7. Factor of Safety under external loading (8 kN/m²)

This section presents the FS results under additional external loading conditions, combined with groundwater influence, for both natural and vegetated slopes.

Table S7. Factor of Safety (FS) under external loading with groundwater (8 kN/m²)

Slope (H:V)	MH	CH	ML	MH (Vetiver)	CH (Vetiver)	ML (Vetiver)
0.5:1	1.407	1.795	1.056	1.377	1.71	1.45
1:01	1.727	2.077	1.41	1.738	2.086	1.448
1.75:1	2.069	2.377	1.792	2.057	2.375	1.79

Note: External loading reduces FS values compared to baseline conditions; however, Vetiver reinforcement contributes to maintaining stability (FS > 1.0), highlighting its effectiveness under anthropogenic loading.

S8. Displacement under external loading (8 kN/m²)

This section includes displacement results obtained under combined groundwater and external loading conditions.

Table S8. Total displacement under external loading with groundwater (mm)

Slope (H:V)	MH	CH	ML	MH (Vetiver)	CH (Vetiver)	ML (Vetiver)
0.5:1	17.56	363.8	5.201	22.27	87.84	134.9
1:01	37.48	602.4	10.82	14.74	240.7	19.68
1.75:1	452.9	57.45	328.9	705.4	2640	183

Note: The results reveal that deformation behavior is highly dependent on soil type and loading conditions. In some cases, vegetation reduces displacement, while in others, complex soil–root interactions lead to localized increases in deformation.

S9. Factor of Safety under combined seismic and loading conditions

This section presents FS results under multi-hazard conditions, combining seismic loading, external loading, and groundwater influence.

Table S9. Factor of Safety (FS) under seismic and loading conditions with groundwater

Slope (H:V)	MH	CH	ML	MH (Vetiver)	CH (Vetiver)	ML (Vetiver)
0.5:1	0.624	0.757	0.781	0.877	1.538	1.43
1:01	0.903	0.587	0.217	0.611	2.06	1.44
1.75:1	0.311	4.709	0.856	1.929	2.087	0.715

Note: FS values below 1.0 indicate instability. The results demonstrate that Vetiver reinforcement can significantly improve slope stability under multi-hazard conditions, particularly in CH soils, where transitions from unstable to stable states are observed.

S10. Displacement under combined seismic and loading conditions

This section reports displacement results under the most critical scenario, combining seismic loading, external forces, and groundwater conditions.

Table S10. Total displacement under seismic and loading conditions with groundwater (mm)

Slope (H:V)	MH	CH	ML	MH (Vetiver)	CH (Vetiver)	ML (Vetiver)
0.5:1	39.59	863.2	7.035	34.95	97.64	136.8
1:01	71.72	2133	70.31	41.95	243.7	19.79
1.75:1	3012	29	688.9	752.3	3004	458.3

Note: All simulations include seismic loading, external surcharge, and groundwater conditions. Displacement varied notably with soil type and slope geometry, with the highest values observed in steep MH slopes. Vetiver reduced displacement in several cases, although its effect remained configuration-dependent under multi-hazard conditions.